

How *far* are we from keeping everyone warm in cost-of-living crisis? Measuring geographic accessibility to UK warm spaces

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Summary

Warm Welcome Spaces provide safe and warm environments for vulnerable populations during winter months amid the cost-of-living crisis in the UK. Understanding the spatial coverage and accessibility of WWS is essential for effective planning and management of these services. This study demonstrates how we are using spatial accessibility measures and GIS-based dashboard to support the planning of Warm Welcome Spaces. We measure accessibility using the cumulative opportunity method, validate results against survey data, and develop a web-based dashboard to support decision-making. The results show that 66.24% population can access at least one warm welcome spaces within 30-minute walk. The findings and tools have informed local authorities and community organisations in management and planning of WWS networks.

KEYWORDS: warm welcome space, spatial accessibility, dashboard, GIS, fuel poverty

1 Introduction

Fuel poverty in the UK (defined as inability to afford adequate warmth at home; Bradshaw and Hutton (1983)) has been a persistent societal challenge in the UK in recent years, which is exacerbated by rising fuel prices, low incomes, and energy-inefficient housing (Ramsden, 2020). In the year of 2022, over 3.2 million households in England (13.2% of all households) were estimated to experience fuel poverty (Department for Energy Security and Net Zero, 2019). In response to this challenge, local authorities and community organisations have established Warm Welcome Spaces (WWS) to provide safe and warm environments for individuals to stay warm and connected to the community during winter months. By 2024, the networks of WWS consisted of over 5,300 venues in the UK, with over annual 2.6 million visits. These public venues include libraries, community centres, and faith buildings.

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Managing and planning the WWS network requires an understanding of the geographical coverage of and accessibility to these spaces. Geographic information systems (GIS) provide efficient and easy-to-use tools to measure and visualise geospatial accessibility to WWS at varying spatial scales. For the first time in literature, this study aims to demonstrate the application of GIS methods and techniques to assess the spatial accessibility of WWS in the UK. This work includes selecting and tuning the appropriate accessibility measures, validating the accessibility results, and developing a data dashboard for supporting decision-making. The findings can inform local authorities and community organisations in strategic planning of WWS network and improving targeted outreach efforts to ensure that vulnerable populations are aware of and accessible to these essential services.

2 Measuring and validating spatial accessibility to warm spaces

2.1 Measuring spatial accessibility to warm spaces

Spatial accessibility represents the potential ease of reaching a service or facility from a given location. A large and growing body of literature has investigated the definition and measurement of spatial accessibility, which results in a wide range of GIS-based spatial accessibility methods. However, as noted by Silva et al. (2017), there exists a significant gap between the advances in scientific research on accessibility and its effective application in planning practice. Such issue is observed in this project: after we proposed several accessibility measures (including cumulative opportunity and two-step floating catchment area) to Warm Welcome Campaign (WWC) that manages WWS, the WWC team was concerned about the interpretability of these measures and their real relevance to the planning needs. After discussion, we agreed to focus on the accumulative opportunity measure, which is straightforward, easy-to-compute, and easy-to-understand for practitioners. This measure calculates the total number of WWS that can be reached within a given travel cost (e.g. distance or time) from a given location (Santana Palacios & El-Geneidy, 2022). It is defined as below:

$$A_i = \sum_{j \in \{j | C_{ij} \leq T\}} C_{ij} D_j \quad (1)$$

where A_i represents the accessibility to WWS at location i , C_{ij} is the travel cost (based on distance or time) from location i to WWS venue j , and D_j is the capacity (e.g. maximum number of visitors) of WWS venue j . This capacity is set to 1 for all venues as it is observed that most venues have sufficient space to accommodate visitors. T represents the catchment area size of WWS or the maximum travel cost that people are willing to endure to access WWS. This parameter is based on either distance (e.g. 5 km) or travel mode and time (e.g. 15 minutes by walking or public transport). Here, we define the WWS catchment area size as 30-minute walking distance, as most people access warm spaces by walking rather than driving or via public transport in order to save costs, according to the survey by WWC.

We calculated the accessibility to WWS at two different levels, including Middle Layer Super Output Area (MSOA) and Local Authority District (LAD). First, the MSOA-level accessibility is calculated by cumulative opportunity method and based on WWS locations and population-weighted centroids of MSOAs. Then, the MSOA-level accessibility results are aggregated by a population-weighted sum

into the LAD level. The LAD-level accessibility results are illustrated in Figure 1. Metropolitan areas, including London, Manchester, and Birmingham, exhibit higher accessibility to WWS compared to rural areas.

Figure 1: Spatial accessibility to warm welcome spaces at LAD level

2.2 Validating spatial accessibility to warm spaces

Validating spatial accessibility is challenging for most planning applications, as spatial accessibility represents a potential measure rather than an observed behaviour. Generally, the observed behaviour of accessing a service is influenced by multiple factors beyond spatial accessibility, such as cultural preferences and service quality. In this project, we assume that spatial accessibility to WWS is closely related to the awareness of WWS in the neighbourhood of a respondent to a survey conducted by WWC. Therefore, we will validate the spatial accessibility results by comparing the proportion of all population with access to at least one WWS within 30-minute walk (66.24%) and the proportion of survey respondents who are aware of WWS in their local area. The validation work is ongoing and the results will be presented in the conference.

3 Data dashboard

A web-based and interactive data dashboard is developed to visualise the spatial accessibility results and support planning of new WWS. In selecting the platform for this dashboard, we considered several options, including CARTO dashboard, ArcGIS Online, and Python Dash. Python Dash was ruled out due to the need for coding skills and maintaining a server, which is infeasible due to the limited technical capacity and human resources. ArcGIS Online was also excluded as it requires a

paid subscription and the interactivity is limited. Finally, CARTO dashboard was selected as we got a two-year free license from CARTO for non-profit use, and this dashboard can be easily shared and accessed via web browsers rather than via installing software or coding. A screenshot of the dashboard is shown in Figure 2. This dashboard has been used by WWC and local authorities in identifying areas with low accessibility to WWS and planning new WWS locations.

Figure 2: Warm Welcome dashboard screenshot

4 Conclusions and future works

This ongoing project applies spatial accessibility measures and GIS-based dashboard to support the planning and management of Warm Welcome Spaces in the UK. It represents a case study where the academic knowledge of spatial accessibility is translated into practical planning of a key social infrastructure to support vulnerable populations and highlights the value of GIS in addressing societal challenges. In future works, we plan to refine the accessibility measures by considering the share of multiple travel modes (e.g. walking, public transport, cycling, and driving) and incorporating the urban-rural differences in using and accessing WWS. We also plan to conduct fine-grained validation of the accessibility results by conducting extra survey data within WWS users.

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Biographies

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